

Evaluation Polluted by Some Heavy Elements in Blood Serum Patients Admitted to Al-Rifai General Hospital in Al-Rifai City Located South of the Al-Garraf Oil Field

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Suggested Citation

Ali, A.S. (2024). Evaluation Polluted by Some Heavy Elements in Blood Serum Patients Admitted to Al-Rifai General Hospital in Al-Rifai City Located South of the Al-Garraf Oil Field. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 305-313.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(6\).24](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(6).24)

Abstract:

This study period was from January 2021 to December 2022 for the purpose of measuring the average of some Heavy metals in the serum in People who visited Al-Rifai General Hospital in Al-Rifai district, north of Dhi Qar Governorate located near the Garraf oil field (the north of governorate). Collection of 40 samples with age ranged from (19 years to 60 years) years, it was divided into three groups, and the study adopted 15 samples of People who do not have a specific disease as a control group and 13 samples were from people with diabetes and 12 from pregnant women. The results and statistic showed that the concentration rate of heavy metals diabetics higher than the concentration in healthy people (control group) and

pregnant only in the element cadmium did pregnant women have higher concentrations than the rest of the groups. The present study showed the highest concentration rate for heavy metal was for lead in diabetics was with a mean (7.725 ± 2.225534) ng / ml, while the lowest concentration of the element cadmium was in the control group a mean (0.0195 ± 0.008167) ng / ml. In general, the concentration rate in people with diabetes and pregnant women had higher than the concentration rate in control group.

Keywords: Heavy metals (HM), Al-Rifai District, pregnant women, diabetes, Al- Gharraf oil field.

Introduction

Heavy metal (HM) are as elements of the atomic mass is relatively large. HM such as Zn, Cu, As and Co are essential HM and It has an important role in biological processes like as protection against oxidative damage in cellular respiration, genomic stability, immunity, apoptosis and cell signalling. Exposure to high levels of these minerals may cause acute poisoning, cancer, or chronic diseases. (Zheng et al., 2015).

Some previous studies evaluated one single type of heavy metal (HM) exposure and its relationship with health outcomes. This is a limitation however, as there may be complex

interactions between different heavy metal (HM). The literature has shown that different pollutants in the exposure mixture have different effects on health Results, and these mixtures may be a relationship reverse or synergistic (Valeri et al., 2017). Therefore, it is crucial to quantify the synergistic effects of the different HM (Braun et al., 2016) on disease risk using mixture analysis.

Environmental pollution and exposure to harmful metals is a source of concern in all countries of the world. They are encountered or treated because they are released in high quantities into the environment due to human and biological activities. Although these

minerals, in low concentrations, are considered essential micronutrients for living organisms they may lead to harmful effects on the organism (Luque-García et al., 2011).

Some studies conducted so far to estimate the toxicity of trace metals have emphasized the development of analytical methods to determine the most toxic ones in different biological samples like contaminated water, soils, plant and animal tissues, mainly using techniques for elemental analysis (like atomic absorption and emission spectroscopy and inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry being the latter the most widely analytical technique for both multi-elemental analysis and speciation). However, efforts have not been intensified to understand the molecular mechanisms underlying the so-called Heavy metals and the ways in which metals interact in Cells and organs of organisms (Luque-García et al., 2011).

Essential heavy metals are also of great importance to health, but their vital role may vary and be toxic when their concentration rises to high levels in the body. Essential HM have four basic functions Where they act as being stabilizers, elements of structure, essential elements for hormonal function and cofactors to enzyme activity (Kurdoglu et al., 2012).

Heavy Metals (HM) and Harmful Effects on Human Health

The form of HM Biological research showed that exposure to HM It is considered a source of DNA damage to humans. Materials like lead, zinc, arsenic, mercury, iron, nickel etc. enhance DNA mutation or damage. Elements like cadmium, arsenic and nickel are the factors of changes in DNA cell (Jadoon and Malik, 2017). Neurological diseases such as Parkinson disease, carcinoma, skin disorders, rare autoimmune disorder, tumor, degenerative disease and cardiovascular disorders are common examples of damage caused by HM (Caffo et al., 2014; Jadoon and Malik, 2017). The deficiency of essential trace elements in the human body can increase the accumulation of toxic in human Body organs (Bishak et al., 2015). Because heavy metals are non-biodegradable materials, they remain in the environment for a long time. They

also cause changes or destruction in enzymes, proteins, nucleic acids and fats due to their ability to produce free radicals. When heavy metals enter the body, the process of their excretion depends on the presence of some antioxidants such as: α -tocopherol, glutathione, ascorbate etc. Which works to inhibit free radicals, and this is done by changing or obstructing the activity of enzymes such as: peroxidase, catalase and superoxide dismutase. (Jan et al., 2015).

Cd

A link can be formed that links two elements if there is a common source of exposure and sufficiently in biological processes. This link is considered important in the case of exposure to heavy elements and intervention if necessary. For example, a link can be made between the metals cadmium and lead because they are both associated with smoking. This also appears in the metals emitted from car exhausts (Pt, Pd and Rh), as they work in the same manner as environmental pollution. We can expect a link between these elements in the blood and serum, but this has not been proven conclusively (Bárány et al., 2002).

Pb

The immune system is constantly facing many of foreign that disease-causing substances that originate from the surrounding environment. Although the mechanisms underlying its effect have enabled scientists to identify it partially, the effect of some elements, such as lead, remains in need of further clarification. As explained (Metryka et al., 2018) Lead has a devastating effect on the body's immunity. and there is evidence that this metal can enhance the inflammatory response. Also the chemical and molecular processes in the body respond to the inflammatory effect of lead as well as its effect it on cytokine metabolism, (IFN γ), and cancer necrosis elements (TNF- α); Activities and multiplication processes accompanying enzymes involved in inflammation (cyclooxygenases); and the effect on acute phase proteins: C-reactive protein (CRP), haptoglobin, and ceruloplasmin. The effect of lead on the immune system is represented by its effect on (T & B lymphocytes,

macrophages and langerhans cells) Secretion processes of each of histamine, endothelin IgA, IgE and IgG

As

Arsenic It is considered one of the carcinogenic metals found in the environment and occupational settings. It can enter the human body through drinking water, and when exposed to high amounts of this metal, to be infected with different types of cancer or cardiovascular disease, in addition to its effect on the brain's efficiency in children or newborns. Continuous occupational exposure to arsenic may lead to lung cancer. In humans, it was found that there is an inverse relationship between the level of selenium in plasma and the level of arsenic in urine. However, epidemiological studies related to this aspect will not be conclusive. (Janasik et al., 2017).

Ni

Many researchers have investigated the concentration of nickel in hair and blood serum and its relationship to breast cancer, but they have not found consistent results in this regard. Therefore, the researchers conducted a systematic review to re-evaluate this relationship and compare it with rules of healthy controls. The results show the level of nickel was high in the blood serum in cases of breast cancer, and that the treatment did not reduce the level of nickel in the blood serum in a clear way. Nickel levels were also high in the hair of breast cancer patients and were slightly higher than controls. From all of the above, we conclude that high levels of nickel in the blood serum are linked to breast cancer, and that high exposure to nickel is dangerous and may lead to breast cancer. (Yu, M., & Zhang, J. 2017).

Materials and Methods

Sample Collection

The current study included Collect samples from 40 people. (aged from 19 years to 60 years) from People who visited Al-Rifai General Hospital in Al-Rifai district, which is located north of DhiQar Governorate near the Garraf oil field,

north of Nassiriya city the withdrawal area was disinfected with a mild disinfectant, then blood was drawn from the radial vein, 10 ml of blood was obtained:

1. Blood was placed in the EDTA tube.
2. All tubes are transferred in a cold box until the serum is separated for the purpose of estimating heavy metal.

Serum Preparation

10 ml of blood was taken and placed in a centrifuge (3000 rpm/min) for 20 minutes, Then the serum was stored at -20°C until serum was digested to estimate the concentration of heavy metals.

Digestion of Serum

The serum was digested by following the method (Ji and Ren 2002) an adding of 2 ml of Nitric acid (70%) and one ml of Pero-chloric acid (70 %) to 0.5 ml of serum in a pyrex tube then heating of this compound with a water path on a hot plate at 160 °C for 1 hour, then cooled and finally completed to 10 ml with (30%) Hydrochloric acid. Some modifications were done as the soaking of the serum in nitric acid for half an hour, followed by the addition of perchloric acid, and the increment of heating degree and period to 200 °C and 2.5 hours respectively in order to obtain an absolute digestion of serum and vaporization of acids.

Measurement of HM

Heavy metals in the blood serum were measured using an atomic absorption spectrometer (FAAS-Phoenix 986 AA. United kingdom) according to manufacturer's procedures.

Study Area

To determine the probability of contamination of the area by Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), as well as the problem of pollution spread result of combustion operations and human activity, because of the presence of Al-Gharaf oil field, which was officially inaugurated in 2013 at north of Al-Rifai district Thi-Qar province.

Al-Rifai district south of the Al- Gharaf Oil field (see Figure 1 and 2), which are at distance 12.8 km and a displacement 12 km from the oil field.

Results and Discussion

Heavy metal concentrations in blood serum of study samples

The mean concentrations of heavy metals determine for all samples as listed in table (1). The result shows the mean total concentration

of Cd, Pb, As and Ni for healthy people with a mean (0.0199 ± 0.008412 , 6.41 ± 2.116665 , 0.289 ± 0.158048 and 0.178 ± 0.031939) $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$ respectively While, the mean total concentration Cd, Pb, As and Ni for Diabetics with a mean (0.0218 ± 0.009091 , 6.29 ± 2.023134 , 0.438 ± 0.292751 and 0.45 ± 0.372951) $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$, and the mean total concentration of Cd, Pb, As and Ni for Pregnant with a mean (0.025 ± 0.252954 , 5.0895 ± 3.232057 , 0.3095 ± 0.288953 and 0.447 ± 0.296875) $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$ respectively.

Figure 1. The Place of Dhi Qar Governorate in the Map of Iraq

Figure 2. Location of Al -Gharaf oil Field Site from Al -Rifai District

Table 1. Mean Values of Heavy Metals Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$) in Study Samples

	Groups	No.	Mean \pm SD. $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$
Cd $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$	Healthy people exposed to pollution (Control)	15	0.0199 ± 0.008412
	Diabetics	14	0.0298 ± 0.009091
	Pregnant	12	0.025 ± 0.252954
Pb $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$	Healthy people exposed to pollution (Control)	15	6.41 ± 2.116665
	Diabetics	14	6.89 ± 2.023134
	Pregnant	12	5.0895 ± 3.232057
As $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$	Healthy people exposed to pollution (Control)	15	0.289 ± 0.158048
	Diabetics	14	0.438 ± 0.292751
	Pregnant	12	0.3095 ± 0.288953
Ni $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$	Healthy people exposed to pollution (Control)	15	0.178 ± 0.031939
	Diabetics	14	0.45 ± 0.372951
	Pregnant	12	0.447 ± 0.296875

Cadmium (Cd)

The concentration of Cd determines for samples in table (2). The result showed the highest frequent level of Cd concentration in **pregnant**

groups with a mean (0.0645 ± 0.036163) $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$ while, the lowest frequent level of Cd concentration in the control groups with a mean (0.0195 ± 0.008167) $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$.

Table 2. Mean Values of Cd Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$) in Study Samples Depending on the Age Group

Cd $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$	Group age	N0	Mean \pm SD. $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$
Healthy people exposed to pollution (Control)	19-30	5	0.0318 ± 0.010815
	31-41	5	0.0195 ± 0.008167
	42-53	5	0.0221 ± 0.007004
Diabetics	30-40	4	0.02015 ± 0.00634
	41-50	4	0.0196 ± 0.011503
	51-60	5	0.0228 ± 0.009705
Pregnant	18-25	6	0.0399 ± 0.005621
	26-32	6	0.0645 ± 0.036163

Table 3. Correlation Matrix for Cd in Control, Diabetics and Pregnant in Study Stations

	Control	Diabetics	Pregnant
Control	1		
Diabetics	-0.23413	1	
Pregnant	0.259371	-0.14034	1

Lead (Pb)

The concentration of Pb determines to all samples in table (4). The result shows the highest frequent level of Pb concentration in the **diabetics** groups with a mean (7.725 ± 2.225534) $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$ while, the lowest frequent level of Pb concentration in the **control** groups with a mean (5.31 ± 2.565701) $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$.

Table 4. Mean Values of Pb Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$) in Study Samples Depending on the Age Group

Pb $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$	Group age	N0	Mean \pm SD. $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$
Healthy people exposed to pollution (Control)	19-30	5	7.01 ± 1.958239
	31-41	5	5.31 ± 2.565701
	42-53	5	6.41 ± 2.191648
Diabetics	30-40	4	6.7 ± 1.883799
	41-50	4	7.725 ± 2.225534
	51-60	5	6.89 ± 2.20196
Pregnant	18-25	6	5.34 ± 3.577927
	26-32	6	5.6345 ± 2.388043

Table 5. Correlation Matrix for Pb in Control, Diabetics and Pregnant in Study Stations

	Control	Diabetics	Pregnant
Control	1		
Diabetics	0.185917	1	
Pregnant	0.049783	-0.29711	1

Arsenic (As)

The concentration of As for samples in table (6). The result showed the highest frequent level of As concentration in the Diabetics groups with a mean (0.661 ± 0.276793) $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$ while, the lowest frequent level of As concentration in the **control** groups with a mean (0.281 ± 0.103241) $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$.

Table 6. Mean Values of As Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$) in Study Samples Depending on the Age Group

As $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$	Group age	N0	Mean \pm SD. $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$
Healthy people exposed to pollution (Control)	19-30	5	0.321 ± 0.096349
	31-41	5	0.372 ± 0.213694
	42-53	5	0.281 ± 0.103241
Diabetics	30-40	4	0.4685 ± 0.339011
	41-50	4	0.661 ± 0.276793
	51-60	5	0.419 ± 0.275802
Pregnant	18-25	6	0.3795 ± 0.263812
	26-32	6	0.396 ± 0.138758

Table 7. Correlation Matrix for As in Control, Diabetics and Pregnant in Study Stations

	Control	Diabetics	Pregnant
Control	1		
Diabetics	-0.32536	1	
Pregnant	0.157523	-0.54796	1

Ni

The concentration of **Ni** determines for samples in table (4). The result shows the highest frequent level of **Ni** concentration in the **diabetics** groups with a mean (0.67 ± 0.382666) $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$ while, the lowest frequent level of **Ni** concentration in the **control** groups with a mean (0.166 ± 0.019583) $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$.

Table 8. Mean Values of Ni Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$) in Study Samples Depending on the Age Group

Ni $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$	Group age	N0	Mean \pm SD. $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$
Healthy people exposed to pollution (Control)	19-30	5	0.177 ± 0.043985
	31-41	5	0.189 ± 0.027414
	42-53	5	0.166 ± 0.019583
Diabetics	30-40	4	0.67 ± 0.382666
	41-50	4	0.54 ± 0.469432
	51-60	5	0.59 ± 0.335515
Pregnant	18-25	6	0.53 ± 0.237943
	26-32	6	0.504 ± 0.166333

Table 9. Correlation Matrix for Ni in Control, Diabetics and Pregnant in Study Stations

	Control	Diabetics	Pregnant
Control	1		
Diabetics	-0.08869	1	
Pregnant	-0.09164	-0.36412	1

Discussion

Heavy Metals Concentration in Blood Serum

Cadmium

The current study results showed highest frequent level of Cd concentration was in the pregnant group with a mean (0.0645 ± 0.036163) $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$ while, the lowest frequent level of Cd concentration was control groups with a mean (0.0195 ± 0.008167) $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$, results indicate that

Cd blood level is rather close to the health-based level of (0.0645 µg/L) (0.0195 µg/dl), proposed by WHO. This may be due to the fact that cadmium that enters the blood through pulmonary and internal pathways rapidly clears from the circulation, depositing mainly in the liver and kidney (Adnan et al., 2012). while in this study is inconsistent with the study conducted by (Bulat et al., 2009) in Serbia, where the blood concentration levels in exposed workers Cadmium pollution ranged between (7.0 and 18.9 µg/L) (0.7 and 1.89 µg/dl), and study conducted by Yaseen et al., (2014) in Baghdad, where they found that the concentration of cadmium in the serum blood of workers with a mean (6.418 ± 0.636 µg/l) (80.641 ± 60.063 µg/dl) , results of this study are significantly higher than the results of the current study.

Lead

This study results showed that the concentration rate highest frequent level of Pb concentration was in the Diabetics group with a mean (7.725 ± 2.225534) µg/dl while, the lowest frequent level of Pb concentration was in the control group with a mean (5.31 ± 2.565701) µg/dl, the results of the present study also showed statistically significant differences at (p≤0.05) between the mean Pb concentrations of workers compared to healthy people.

The mean blood serum Pb concentration observed in the present study is higher than (2.512 µg/dl) reported by (Junaid et al., 2016) for the level of Pb in the blood serum of workers who work in from surgical instrument manufacturing in Pakistan. In California he conducted (Governor et al .,2017)study showed that the average lead concentration for workers' blood was (17.8 µg/dl) . A study showed by Kim et al., (2014) in Korea the workers blood serum lead levels were 7 µg/dL and 6 µg/dL in the “Manufacturers of Rubber and Plastic Products” and the “Manufacture of Basic Metal Products” division, respectively. In Thailand, a study by Lormphongs et al., 2003) was conducted in a battery manufacturing plant where Pb was used in the processes of production, the average level of Pb in the biological samples of workers was 22.3 µg/dL.

The discrepancy with previous studies and between this study may be due to several reasons, one of which may depend on the level and period of exposure to lead (Moshchil, 2016).

Arsenic

This study results showed that the concentration rate highest frequent level of arsenic concentration was in the Diabetics group with a mean (0.661 ± 0.276793) µg/dl while, the lowest frequent level of arsenic concentration was in the Control group with a mean (0.281 ± 0.103241) µg/dl, the results were within the permissible limits of the WHO in all study groups. The present study is consistent with the study conducted by (Yuan et al ., 2020). Associations between renal functions and exposure of arsenic and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon in adults living near a petrochemical The arsenic rate was (0.68 to 0.49µg/dl).

The results of this study are inconsistent with the results of the study conducted by (Yüksel et al.,2018) in Turkey to measure the concentration of arsenic in samples blood serum of metal workers, where As concentration in the blood of workers was with a mean (2.125 µg/dl), this result is higher than the result this study

Nickel

The results of this study showed that the highest frequent level of Ni concentration in the diabetics group with a mean (0.67 ± 0.382666) µg/dl while, the lowest frequent level of Ni concentration in the control group with a mean (0.166 ± 0.019583) µg/dl. Consistent this study is with the study conducted by (Afridi et al.,2006) to evaluate toxic heavy metals in blood serum of steelworkers, where Ni concentration in the blood of production and quality control workers was (0.407 and 0.331 µg/dl) respectively. The mean blood serum Ni concentration observed in this study was lower than (0.094 µg/dl) reported by Iyanda, (2018) in Bangladesh to measure the levels of heavy metals in biological samples in people working at gas stations. Serum nickel concentrations were not significantly influenced by age or sex.

Conclusion

This study investigated the levels of four elements (Cd, Pb, As and Ni) in the serum of the people who live near the the Al-Gharraf oil field. The present study was recorded high values of these metals in blood serum of diabetics in compared with the its concentration in the other groups. There was also a variation in the concentration of metals among the other groups. Different values of the concentration of these heavy metals when compared to global studies that recorded a wide range of variation according to the time and place of sample collection was record. However, all the metal concentrations collected were within the internationally permissible limit.

Reference

- Bárány, E., Bergdahl, I. A., Bratteby, L. E., Lundh, T., Samuelson, G., Schütz, A., & Oskarsson, A. (2002). Relationships between trace element concentrations in human blood and serum. *Toxicology Letters*, *134*(1-3), 177-184. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-4274\(02\)00196-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-4274(02)00196-3)
- Bishak, Y. K., Payahoo, L., Osatdrahimi, A., & Nourazarian, A. (2015). Mechanisms of cadmium carcinogenicity in the gastrointestinal tract. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, *22*(1), 9-21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-014-3147-3>
- Braun, J. M., Gennings, C., Hauser, R., & Webster, T. F. (2016). What can epidemiological studies tell us about the impact of chemical mixtures on human health? *Environmental Health Perspectives*, *125*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP412>
- Caffo, M., Caruso, G., La Fata, G., Barresi, V., Visalli, M., Venza, M., & Venza, I. (2014). Heavy metals and epigenetic alterations in brain tumors. *Current Genomics*, *15*(6), 457-463. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1389202915666140807214430>
- Governor, B. J., Director, D. S. K., Payne, S., Jackson, R., & Materna, B. (2017). Blood lead levels in California workers. *California Department of Public Health*, *12*(January), 119-122.
- Hawkes, S. J. (1997). What is a "heavy metal"? *Journal of Chemical Education*, *74*(11), 1374. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ed074p1374>
- Hayes, R. B. (1997). The carcinogenicity of metals in humans. *Cancer Causes & Control*, *8*(3), 371-385. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1018417106517>
- Jadoon, S., & Malik, A. (2017). DNA damage by heavy metals in animals and human beings: An overview. *Biochemistry and Pharmacology: Open Access*, *6*(3), 335-339. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2167-0501.1000235>
- Jan, A. T., Azam, M., Siddiqui, K., Ali, A., & Choi, I. (2015). Heavy metals and human health: Mechanistic insight into toxicity and counter defense system of antioxidants. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, *16*(12), 29592-29630. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms161226183>
- Janasik, B., Zawisza, A., Malachowska, B., Fendler, W., Stanislawska, M., Kuras, R., & Wasowicz, W. (2017). Relationship between arsenic and selenium in workers occupationally exposed to inorganic arsenic. *Journal of Trace Elements in Medicine and Biology*, *42*, 76-80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtemb.2017.03.004>
- Junaid, M., Hashmi, M. Z., Zaffar, A., & Malik, R. N. (2016). Evaluating levels and health risk of heavy metals in exposed workers from surgical instrument manufacturing industries of Sialkot, Pakistan. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, *23*(18), 18010-18026. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-016-7001-5>
- Kim, J. H., Kim, E. A., Koh, D. H., Byun, K., Ryu, H. W., & Lee, S. G. (2014). Blood lead levels of Korean lead workers in 2003-2011. *Annals of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, *26*(1), 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2052-4374-26-29>
- Kurdoglu, Z., Kurdoglu, M. E., Demir, H., & Sahin, H. G. (2012). Serum trace elements and heavy metals in polycystic ovary syndrome. *Human & Experimental Toxicology*, *31*(5), 452-456. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0960327111431001>

- Lormphongs, S., Miyashita, K., Morioka, I., Chaikittiporn, C., Miyai, N., & Yamamoto, H. (2003). Lead exposure and blood lead level of workers in a battery manufacturing plant in Thailand. *Industrial Health*, 41(4), 348-353. <https://doi.org/10.2486/indhealth.41.348>
- Luque-Garcia, J. L., Cabezas-Sanchez, P., & Camara, C. (2011). Proteomics as a tool for examining the toxicity of heavy metals. *Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, 30(5), 703-716. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2010.11.013>
- McNeely, M. D., Nechay, M. W., & Sunderman Jr, F. W. (1972). Measurements of nickel in serum and urine as indices of environmental exposure to nickel. *Clinical Chemistry*, 18(9), 992-995.
- Metryka, E., Chibowska, K., Gutowska, I., Falkowska, A., Kupnicka, P., Barczak, K., & Baranowska-Bosiacka, I. (2018). Lead (Pb) exposure enhances expression of factors associated with inflammation. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 19(6), 1813. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms19061813>
- Moshchil, F. A. (2016). Study of some heavy metals concentration and blood parameters of workers in fuel stations in the center of Thi-Qar Province, Southern Iraq. *Thi-Qar University Journal*.
- Valeri, L., Mazumdar, M. M., Bobb, J. F., Henn, B. C., Rodrigues, E., Sharif, O. I., Kile, M. L., & Yu, M. (2017). Serum and hair nickel levels and breast cancer: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *Biological Trace Element Research*, 179(1), 32-37. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12011-017-0990-1>
- Yuan, T. H., Ke, D. Y., Wang, J. E. H., & Chan, C. C. (2020). Associations between renal functions and exposure of arsenic and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon in adults living near a petrochemical complex. *Environmental Pollution*, 256, 113457. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2019.113457>
- Yüksel, B., Şen, N., Türksoy, V. A., Tutkun, E., & Söylemezoğlu, T. (2018). Effect of exposure time and smoking habit on arsenic levels in biological samples of metal workers in comparison with controls. *Marmara Pharmaceutical Journal*, 22(2), 218-226. <https://doi.org/10.12991/mpj.2018.54>
- Zheng, G., Wang, L., Guo, Z., Sun, L., Wang, L., Wang, C., & Qiu, H. (2015). Association of serum heavy metals and trace element concentrations with reproductive hormone levels and polycystic ovary syndrome in a Chinese population. *Biological Trace Element Research*, 167(1), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12011-015-0270-4>